

ISic0803

Dedication by a pair of sevirii

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

sandstone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag, James Cummings, James Chartrand, Valeria Vitale, Michael Metcalfe

Autopsy

2011.06.15

Last Change

2017-08-22 - Jonathan Prag revised the EpiDoc in line with new lapidario catalogue and added images

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Block A was excavated on 22 September 1970, close to one of the internal columns of the west portico, lying on the pavement of

the portico in front of and
between rooms 5 and 6. Block B was excavated in 1971, found
against one of the internal
columns of the west portico, in front of and between rooms 2
and 3. Both can be attributed
to the remains of a base in situ against the rear wall of the
portico between rooms 5 and 6.

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa

Physical Description

Two blocks of yellow, non-local sandstone (Burgio 2013: 26 n.2), surmounted by a
cornice and forming the left and right ends of the upper
part of a monument /
statue base which originally stood against the internal
rear wall of the west
portico, between rooms 5 and 6. Block A has moulding
around the front, left and
rear upper edges, but presents a smooth vertical face on
the right side (where a
missing block joined it). Remains of fixing holes for one
or more statues are
visible on the upper surface, as is the hole for a metal
staple for attachment
to the rest of the monument. The block is 35 cm high, 69
cm wide across the top
of the moulding, 58 cm wide across the base, depth 68
cm across the top, 47 cm
across the base. The epigraphic field below the moulding
is 17.5 cm high and 58
cm wide. Block B has a moulding around the front, right
and rear upper edges,
and a smooth vertical face on the left side (where a
missing block joined it).
Remains of fixing holes for one or more statues are
visible on the upper
surface, as is a hole for a metal staple for attachment to
the rest of the

monument. Height 35 cm, width 42 cm across the base,
53 cm across the top, depth
47 cm across the base, 68 cm across the top.

Dimensions

Height 35 cm

Width 182 cm

Depth 68 cm

Layout

Two lines of Latin letters in the field below the moulding (17.5 cm high and
originally 160 cm wide)

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are crudely cut (but the stone is too coarse to allow of better): P is
open, but R is closed; Q has a long tail; long I is taller than
the other letters
(63mm); E is tall and narrow; words are separated by simple
interpuncts.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 45-55 mm

Line 2: 40-45 mm

Interlineation

Not measured: mm

Text

1. Q (uintus) · Caecilius · Q (uinti) · I (ibertus) · Hime
[raeus.....]s · Ɔ (mulieris) · I (ibertus) · Sabinus ·
(vac.undefined)
2. (vac.undefined)s ę yiri · (vac.unknown) [.....] ɔ
(e) · s (ua) · p (ecunia) · (vac.undefined)

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Quintus Caecilius Himeraeus, freedman of Quintus [and (praenomen + nomen)]
Sabinus, freedman of a
woman, sevirs [---] (set this up) at their own expense.

Commentary

Part of the base of the original monument remains in situ in the portico, and Burgio (2013) has reconstructed the monument in its totality. This reconstruction demonstrates that one block is missing between the two surviving blocks of the crown of the base, and that the missing block was 60 cm wide (with the same height (35 cm) and depth (47 cm across the base and 68 cm across the top with the moulding) as the other two blocks). The lacuna therefore between the two surviving parts of the text was 60 cm. In line 1, this lacuna was almost certainly filled by the word *et* ('and') and the praenomen and nomen of the second individual with the cognomen Sabinus. In line 2, the presence of a gap before and after the word *seviri* suggests that there were fewer, widely spaced words in line 2. Two possibilities can be suggested: either the name in the accusative of the divinity to whom the monument was dedicated, and whom the statue or statue group on top depicted (e.g. AE 1990 no.225-226, a dedication to Victoria Augusta at Iuvanum in Samnium); or else just the word *Augustales*, i.e. *seviri Augustales* (e.g. AE 2007 no.698, Huesca in Spain and AE 1981 no.345, Etruria).

The gens Caecilia is attested at Halaesa in Cicero (Verr. 2.2.23, Q. Caecilius Dio) and on the Augustan coinage (RPC I, no. 628-629, Caecilius Rufus, duumvir) and elsewhere on the island (see Facella 2006: 234 n. 87; 250; 287-288). The cognomen Himeraeus is attested at Termini Imerese (anc. Thermae Himeraeae), in I.L.Termini no.90 with p.61 ([-] Domitius A.f. Quir. Himeraeus). The cognomen Sabinus is attested in Sicily at Messina (I.Messina no.7: M. Saufei Sabinus), Catania (CIL 10 no.7062: Crassicius Sabinus Aptitianus) and at Taormina (IG 14 no.166: Auxanon son of Sabinos).

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Photo J. Prag